

H²IOSC
Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud

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Abstract

This document describes the activities completed in the H2IOSC WP8 – *Training, Capacity Building, Engagement* by the UUOO involved. After describing the internal personnel upskilling, this document reports on the training activities aimed at the SSH community at large and the design process of two training platforms developed according to the shared FAIR-by-Design Methodology. Finally, it describes the dissemination and engagement activities within the scope of the WP8, and it highlights the collaborations originated from said activities. This Deliverable is a report on the project as of October 31st, 2025, which is not yet concluded. The project will conclude on April 30, 2026. Some key features have not yet been developed and completed, but will be in the coming months, such as the ability to distribute DOIs in the H2IOSC Training Library; the possibility of issuing certifications via the European Digital Credentials from the H2IOSC Training Environment, and, the setup of the two platforms on H2IOSC's new Data Centre and their connection with the H2IOSC Marketplace.

Table of Contents

ABSTRACT.....	2
LIST OF ACRONYMS.....	4
LIST OF FIGURES AND TABLES	6
SECTION: INTERNAL TRAINING: PROFESSIONAL UPSKILLING OF H2IOSC PERSONNEL.....	6
INTRODUCTION	6
INTERNAL TRAINING: PROFESSIONAL UPSKILLING OF H2IOSC PERSONNEL.....	7
EXTERNAL TRAINING: TEACHING THE H2IOSC USERS COMMUNITY.....	10
TARGET AUDIENCE	11
DISCIPLINARY AREAS.....	12
METHODOLOGY DEVELOPMENT	18
SOFTWARE IMPLEMENTATION: BUILDING H2IOSC TRAINING INFRASTRUCTURE.....	20
H2IOSC TRAINING ENVIRONMENT - LMS.....	22
H2IOSC TRAINING LIBRARY – REPOSITORY	22
METADATA SCHEMA.....	23
MAPPING AND HARVESTING ON H2IOSC MARKETPLACE.....	25
DISSEMINATION AND ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES.....	26
COLLABORATIONS AND NETWORKING.....	30
CONCLUSIONS.....	36
REFERENCES.....	38

LIST OF ACRONYMS

CLARIN-IT	Italian node of CLARIN - Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
DARIAH-IT	Italian node of DARIAH - Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
E-RIHS.it	Italian node of E-RIHS on Heritage Science
ERIC	European Research Infrastructures Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
H2IOSC	Humanities and Heritage Open Science Cloud
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
OPERAS-IT	Italian node of OPERAS - Open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

LIST OF FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1	Training and Capacity Building	Section: Internal Training: Professional Upskilling of H2IOSC Personnel
Figure 2	RDA Recommendations for a Minimal Metadata Set to Aid Harmonised Discovery of Learning Resources	Section: Metadata Schema
Table 1	Training Analytics	Attachment
Table 2	Training and Engagement Activities Spreadsheet	Attachment

Introduction

The H2IOSC project aims at creating a national infrastructure for the Humanities and heritage in Italy, federating the existing national nodes of the four European infrastructures of the domain, CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS and OPERAS. Work Package 8 of the H2IOSC project is dedicated to “**Training, Capacity Building, Engagement**”, and aims to:

1. **empower user communities** with interdisciplinary and domain-specific FAIR and Open Science skills and competences, as well as training them on what disciplinary infrastructures can offer them at the national and international level. This enables them **to better use the services of the RIs national nodes, of the ERICs and of the national H2IOSC marketplace**, as well as become capable of **correctly managing the lifecycle of their data**;
2. **train a pool of new professionals** such as data stewards, data curators, and trainers, that can support and train future generations of scholars and professionals of trainers, that can support and train future generations of scholars and professionals on **to integrate RIs in their methods and practices**, thus **fostering a change of mentality** in research and possibly industry.

WP8 interacts closely with all other components of the project to ensure coherent communication, dissemination, and training. It builds on the landscaping and community mapping activities of WP2, which identify both the training needs of target audiences and the reference ecosystems for dissemination. WP8 also aligns with WP5, as all services and outputs ultimately converge in the H2IOSC Marketplace; this requires coordination on metadata structures, vocabularies, and descriptors to ensure consistency across published resources. WP8 supports the visibility and uptake of results from WP3 (standardisation), WP4 (platform policies), and WP6 (legal and licensing frameworks), acting as a transversal enabler of outreach and engagement across the infrastructures.

This Deliverable outlines the internal upskilling activities carried out for H2IOSC personnel and the design of two training platforms (the Training Environment and the Training Library), both developed according to the FAIR-by-Design methodology. It also describes external training actions targeted at various audiences (students, teachers, researchers, and professionals) covering a wide range of disciplines within the Social Sciences and Humanities and Cultural Heritage sector. Finally, it presents dissemination and networking initiatives, highlighting collaborations at both national and international levels.

Internal Training: Professional Upskilling of H2IOSC Personnel

To equip the H2IOSC personnel with interdisciplinary and domain-specific competences, the UU00 have organised multiple training activities aimed at internal capacity building, namely focused on data management, open science best practices and instructional design for learners. On a total of 79 training events, 13 of them were dedicated to the upskilling of the H2IOSC personnel. This ratio is highlighted in the chart below, distinguishing “training” initiatives directed to external stakeholders and “capacity building” aimed at the project personnel.

Figure 1 - Training and Capacity Building

These initiatives supported transversal upskilling of the H2IOSC personnel and fostered the exchange of competencies among the RIs involved. Namely, the initiatives included workshops on practical skills, such as:

- Modelling systems development and management
- Programming
- Data visualisation
- Data Science
- Technology transfer with a focus on patent protection
- Digitisation of cultural heritage, from the planning of a campaign to data management
- Service Management
- Data Management
- Instructional Design for Learners

And webinars dedicated to specific platforms and tools, like:

- Database MySQL
- Javascript
- Custom platform on critical edition

One vibrant event was the H2IOSC Cafés series, aimed at creating a network of shared practices among the four RIs. The series consisted of four online seminars¹, each held by one of the RIs involved in the project, with national and European representatives of the four RIs, to disseminate the services developed by CLARIN ERIC, DARIAH ERIC, E-RIHS ERIC and their national nodes and OPERAS.it. Another key event for H2IOSC staff training were the training days organised by OPERAS.it at the Institute for the History of Modern Philosophical and Scientific Thought (ISPF) in Naples, which focused on the services offered by OPERAS.²

¹ <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/h2iosc-cafe-presenting-e-rihs/>, <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/h2iosc-cafe-presenting-operas/>, <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/h2iosc-cafe-dariah/>, <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/h2iosc-cafe-clarin/>

² Programme of the OPERAS training included: Elena Giglia: *Open Science, Open Access, FAIR data: principles, practices and tools for humanities research. OPERAS, an infrastructure for Open Science in the humanities*;

Simone Aliprandi: *Copyright, general principles and applications in the field of humanities research*; Alfredo Corrao: *The basis of the digital object: image files and their characteristics*; Marco Scarbaci: *Introduction to TEI and Introduction to XML metalanguage*; Margherita Porena: *Representation of information, Ontologies for Cultural Heritage*; Giovanna Garofalo: *Metadata: purposes and types General principles of digital archive management*; Margherita Bartoli: *Introduction to Digital Libraries: definition and basic concepts; Architecture and infrastructure of Digital Libraries; Conceptual and descriptive models of a Digital Library*.

External Training: Teaching the H2IOSC Users Community

Since empowering user communities is a key objective in WP8, most of the effort was poured into providing external stakeholders with training on how to integrate the tools offered by the four infrastructures in their research activities, and how to manage their data according to the Open Science best practices.

In the following subsections is a breakdown of the target audience reached by the training and of the disciplinary areas covered.

Target Audience

The training activities were directed at a variety of public audience types, spanning from students and educators to research professionals and the general public. Below is an overview of the audience categories identified, grouped by audience type.

- **University students:** this includes undergraduate and postgraduate students. Some training events, such as open seminars and workshops, were accessible to students interested in the topics, even if not exclusively designed for them.
- **Teachers and trainers:** academic professors were the main target, but several training sessions were organised to equip high school teachers with digital humanities skills and materials to upgrade their teaching.
- **Researchers:** including scholars, PhD candidates and research staff in the humanities and cultural heritage fields. These sessions often focused on advanced topics and were designed to enhance professional research skills, particularly for early-career researchers.

- **Professionals:** non-academic professionals and stakeholders, for example, those from industries, cultural heritage institutions or in the GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums) sectors. WP8 hosted events to engage professionals from both the private and public sectors, emphasising practical applications of research outputs and fostering collaboration.
- **Data stewards, data librarians, data manager:** one of the main goals of WP8 was to train a new pool of professionals, such as data stewards, data librarians and trainers, to support the next generation of researchers in a train-the-trainers perspective.
- **General public:** a broader audience of interested members of the public. A few training events, often offered as public seminars or workshops, were openly advertised and accessible to anyone, aiming to raise awareness and disseminate knowledge beyond the academic field.

Each training session was tailored to its audience category or multiple categories. By addressing students, teachers, researchers, professionals, and the general public through various training formats, such as webinars, summer schools, workshops, and in-person courses, WP8 successfully engaged a broad spectrum of participants in its open science and humanities initiatives. This approach ensured that the training content was accessible and relevant to each public category, from classroom educators and young learners to expert scholars and industry stakeholders, maximising the project's impact on its user communities.

Disciplinary Areas

The training activities covered both general and specific disciplines in the broader field of Social Sciences and Humanities. Each RI engaged with different experts to enrich the training offer and allow the selected audience to learn and apply new methods and tools. The general disciplines covered spanned from computational text processing, knowledge graphs and digital bibliography, digital scholarly editing, and digital humanities methodologies. Each of these disciplines was addressed through specific training activities to maximise the audience engagement. Below is a detailed description of the topics covered under each discipline.

Computational Text Processing. This discipline focuses on techniques for processing and analysing text using computational methods. Training activities in this area covered:

- using Python scripting to read and manipulate raw text: this included fundamental text processing tasks and string manipulation operations on textual data;
- natural language processing (NLP) libraries for text analysis: introduction to NLP libraries and digital humanities-oriented software tools for text analysis. Participants learned to use existing NLP frameworks to perform tasks like tokenisation, PoS tagging and more advanced text analysis;
- structured text encoding and XML processing: techniques for handling texts in structured formats. This included processing XML-encoded documents and transforming them using XSLT (Extensible Stylesheet Language for Transformations). Trainees practised working with textual data marked up in XML and learned how to extract or convert information via XSLT scripts.

Knowledge Graphs and Digital Bibliography. This discipline involves managing and integrating scholarly data using knowledge graphs and bibliographic tools. Training in this area was centred on the use of WikiData, a collaborative knowledge base, and bibliographic databases in a humanities research context. Key topics included:

- an overview of WikiData as an open knowledge graph and how it can be leveraged for storing and querying information relevant to research in the humanities. Participants were introduced to WikiData's structure and taught how to navigate and contribute to it;
- techniques for transferring and integrating bibliographic data from Zotero, a reference management tool, into WikiData. This topic showed how to take curated bibliographies and make them part of the knowledge graph, linking publications with authors, topics, and other metadata;
- a hands-on *datathon* case study focused on adding scholarly publications in Classical Philology and Codicology to WikiData. This involved improving the presence of bibliographic entries related to Greek and Roman antiquity in WikiData. Trainees learned how such data curation expands the WikiData graph, e.g. adding hundreds of new entries on classical texts and research, and makes it more useful for humanistic studies.

Digital Scholarly Editing. Digital scholarly editing, or digital ecdothics, is the application of digital tools to the traditional field of textual criticism and edition of manuscripts. In H2IOSC training, this discipline was represented by specialised lessons on digital edition techniques. Topics covered under this discipline included sessions led by experts in digital philology and involved collaboration with doctoral programs in Italian Studies, providing both theoretical background and practical insights on:

- fundamental concepts and methodologies for creating Digital Scientific Editions of texts. This included how digital editions differ from traditional print critical editions, the use of standards like XML/TEI for encoding texts, and the tools available for editors to publish and analyse texts digitally;
- detailed examination of real-world digital edition projects. Trainees explored the digital editions of Dante Alighieri's *Divina Commedia* and Giovanni Boccaccio's *Teseida* as case studies. Through these examples, participants saw how scholars have encoded, annotated, and presented these classic works in digital form, learning about the challenges and solutions in digitising complex literary texts.

Digital Humanities Methodologies. This broad discipline encompasses the range of computational methods and tools applied across humanities research. The training activities under this category included a general introduction for educators as well as an in-depth workshop for students and early-career researchers. The specific topics addressed were:

- an introduction to how digital tools are changing humanities research. This covered general concepts of digital humanities, demonstrating how scholars use computers to analyse large volumes of textual or cultural data, build computational models, and visualise information in new ways. For high school teachers, this overview also discusses incorporating digital humanities tools into secondary education;
- methods for working with text corpora in research. For example, one training segment showed how to perform error and pragmatic annotation on a learner *corpus* marking language errors and pragmatic features in student-written texts and discussed the stages and challenges of such tagging processes. Another session

focused on collocation analysis in a corpus. These topics taught participants how to prepare and analyse textual datasets to extract linguistic and semantic patterns;

- using digital tools to analyse literary style and authorship. The training covered stylometry, and participants learned about metrics and software for stylistic analysis, seeing how computers can assist in literary studies, for instance, distinguishing authors or periods based on style;
- principles of organising and storing research data in the humanities: a session on database design demonstrated how to structure data such as bibliographic records, historical data, or linguistic datasets for efficient querying and analysis. This gave attendees insight into building databases or using database tools to manage complex humanities data, e.g. historical archives or linguistic corpora;
- examples of combining datasets and digital tools for specific research questions. One topic was the integration of data in historical phonology, showing how scholars merge linguistic data like ancient pronunciation information with digital analysis methods. This illustrated the interdisciplinary nature of digital humanities, where understanding of subject matter (linguistics, history) meets technical skill in data handling;
- a discussion on creating and using digital scholarly editions, complementing the training on ecdotics. The workshop included a talk on digital scholarly editions of texts, reinforcing how critical texts and manuscripts can be made accessible and interactive through digital platforms;
- a round-table discussion on the broader challenges, opportunities, and ethical considerations in digital humanities research. Different disciplinary perspectives (literature, history, linguistics, etc.) were brought together to discuss issues like data quality, tool usability, collaboration across fields, and sustaining digital projects. This

helped trainees appreciate the state-of-the-art and future directions in digital humanities, emphasising collaboration and problem-solving in research.

Heritage Science. Training activities under this discipline were designed to equip participants from a wide range of backgrounds, i.e. heritage professionals, teachers, students and those from complementary disciplines, with both practical and theoretical skills for investigating and safeguarding tangible and intangible heritage.

A key component of the training in heritage science was the continuation of the “Current Topics in Heritage Science” series through its second and third editions. Post-event materials from these sessions were adapted into interactive training resources, thereby extending the reach and impact of the live events. Topics covered under this discipline included, but were not limited to:

- Modelling approaches in conservation: methods for simulating and predicting material behaviour and deterioration in heritage contexts.
- Scientific methods for heritage diagnostics: introduction to non-invasive and micro-destructive analytical techniques (e.g. holographic interferometry, X-ray tomography, chromatographic analyses) for the study of artworks, monuments and archaeological materials.
- Data management and FAIR principles in heritage research: practices for documenting, storing and sharing analytical results according to open science standards.
- Application of ethics to sampling in cultural heritage research: frameworks for responsible decision-making and stakeholder engagement when collecting material samples.
- Emergency preparedness for heritage collections: planning and response strategies for disasters and complex emergencies.

- Laser cleaning techniques and computational optical microscopy: innovative approaches to the examination and treatment of heritage materials.
- Novel diagnostic approaches for historical engines and industrial heritage: adapting advanced methods to less-studied object types of the heritage field.
- Indigenous heritage in museum collections: integrating community knowledge and perspectives into scientific research and conservation practice.
- Pyrolysis GC-MS for heritage analysis: advanced analytical technique for the characterisation of complex heritage materials.

Through these activities, participants gained insight into cutting-edge scientific tools and cross-disciplinary practices for diagnosis and conservation in the field of cultural heritage.

Each of the above-described discipline-focused trainings provided participants with both conceptual knowledge and hands-on experience in the respective area. By covering topics from programming for text analysis to managing scholarly data and using research infrastructures, the H2IOSC training program ensured a comprehensive skill set for researchers working at the intersection of the humanities and digital technology. The structured approach, going from general introductions to specific case studies, helped trainees see how general disciplines are applied in practice through concrete topics and tools.

Methodology Development

To ensure alignment in designing and adapting reusable training materials, the first output of WP8 was the development of a shared methodology. This was achieved by customising the **FAIR-by-Design Methodology** produced by the **Skills for the European Open Science Commons (Skills4EOSC) project**. The adaptation process involved a fruitful collaboration with the Skills4EOSC personnel dedicated to this task. It resulted in a training for trainers aimed at the H2IOSC working group³ that was held on September 20 and 26, 2024. This module was designed with case studies from the CLARIN-IT perspective, so it took examples from the linguistics domain, but it was intended to be discipline-independent and open to the H2IOSC community of trainers.

The major points taken from the Skills4EOSC methodology were refined from Deliverable 2.2 of the project, called *Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Training Materials*⁴ (page numbers in the following list refer to the referenced Deliverable):

- the implementation of the 6-step workflow of the backwards instructional design empowered with **FAIR principles** in the creation of learning materials, which includes: Prepare, Discover, Design, Produce, Publish, and Verify (p. 31);
- the application of the **Backward Instructional Design**, starting from learning objectives clearly stated and referenced in **Bloom's Taxonomy** (p. 41);
- the description of training materials according to the **Recommendations for a Minimal Metadata Set to Aid Harmonised Discovery of Learning Resources**,

³ Filiposka, S., et al. Fair-by-design Training for the CLARIN Community. 1.0.1, Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13867278>.

⁴ Filiposka, S., et al. D2.2 Methodology for Fair-by-design Training Materials. 1.4, Zenodo, 31 agosto 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8305540>.

developed by **RDA** - Research Data Alliance (pp. 28-29) and further adapted in CLARIN⁵;

- the definition of the **learning object** as the minimum unit to which the RDA metadata set applies (pp. 21-24);
- the hierarchical 6-level structure of aggregated learning content, from the root to the minimal unit: **Learning Path > Course > Section > Unit > Module > Learning Object** (p. 48).

During the project, several courses and modules were published according to this methodology, which was disseminated as well in many events, seminars, conferences and invited talks. These teaching and dissemination activities are further detailed in the next sections.

⁵ See the [Metadata Schema](#) section of this document for further information and references.

Software Implementation: Building H2IOSC Training

Infrastructure

According to the FAIR-by-Design Methodology applied in H2IOSC, learning resources have to be **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable** and **Reusable** for both students and teachers. Those different users have specific needs to be addressed: for example, a student may want to access a course in **e-learning** and be able to highlight and comment on the text, download the slide deck in PDF, or access the recording of the lesson on YouTube. On the other hand, a teacher might prefer to access the editable version of the training materials (such as slide decks in Markdown or data in Excel spreadsheets) and might benefit from a more granular description hierarchy, helping them select the part they want to reuse in their teaching activities.

H2IOSC adopted this dual approach to maximise the impact and reusability of learning resources from a train-the-trainer perspective and produced two types of digital objects: 1) **courses** for students to access in e-learning, and 2) FAIR-compliant **training materials** to be reused by trainers in various contexts. To allow end users to access those digital objects, two platforms were implemented:

- **H2IOSC Training Environment**, providing students with a rich catalogue of courses to be accessed in a collaborative learning experience;
- **H2IOSC Training Library**, offering teachers and trainers a repository for publishing and discovering reusable **training materials** as FAIR digital objects.

Together, they form a complementary ecosystem: one for delivering learning directly, and one for curating reusable materials that enrich long-term teaching and training practices.

H2IOSC Training Environment - LMS

The Training Environment is a **Learning Management System** designed to deliver courses in synchronous and asynchronous formats. It enables students to create accounts, enroll in courses (either open or restricted with access codes), track their learning paths, and obtain certifications. This platform is tailored to learners who want to acquire new competencies interactively. It provides an **active learning environment** where students can engage with multimedia materials (slides, videos, infographics, exercises), participate in online sessions, and communicate with peers and instructors via integrated chat and forum functions. Its primary audience is **students** at undergraduate, graduate, and doctoral levels, as well as professionals who wish to strengthen their skills through structured courses.

Key functionalities:

- Student profiles to manage enrolled courses and certifications.
- Course enrollment (open or closed).
- Multimedia lesson delivery (e.g., slides, interactive text, H5P content).
- Integrated online meeting support (Teams, Zoom, BigBlueButton).
- Interactive note-taking, highlighting, and linking for lessons.
- Teacher-side editing tools to design courses hierarchically (course → module → lesson) following the metadata schema

H2IOSC Training Library – Repository

The **Training Library** is the first repository entirely dedicated to **training materials** as FAIR digital objects. It was designed to store, publish, and disseminate teaching materials in open formats, complete with **metadata**, **persistent identifiers** (PIDs), and **licenses**. It is

developed with FAIR-by-Design methodology, ensuring materials are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The Library addresses a gap in the **European Open Science Cloud** by creating a sustainable infrastructure for teachers and trainers. It allows educators to deposit, discover, and reuse modular training resources, thus creating a community of practice around shared teaching materials. Its two-step review process ensures quality and reliability. The platform primarily targets **teachers and trainers** at the university and professional levels. It supports them in reusing, adapting, and remixing modular **training materials** to enrich their courses.

Key functionalities:

- A back-office interface for uploading materials, organised hierarchically: **Learning Path** → **Course** → **Section** → **Unit** → **Module** → **Learning Object**;
- required metadata fields based on the **RDA Recommendations for a Minimal Metadata Set to Aid Harmonised Discovery of Learning Resources**, enriched with CLARIN extensions (contributors, workload in ECTS, PIDs, etc.);
- automatic PID generation for unpublished materials;
- **licensing** options for clear reuse conditions;
- **faceted search** (by keywords, author, date, topic, language, format);
- **bookmarking** and **citation** export;
- **open access** to published resources, with download enabled via federated login.

Metadata Schema

Following the Skills4EOSC Methodology recommendations, both platforms were designed to describe learning resources with the **Recommendations for a Minimal Metadata Set to**

Aid Harmonised Discovery of Learning Resources⁶. This flexible schema includes three main information categories: descriptive, access and educational, with a total of 14 tags.

Figure 2 - RDA Recommendations for a Minimal Metadata Set to Aid Harmonised Discovery of Learning Resources

This flexible scheme is open to adjustments and additions depending on needs related, for example, to different teaching perspectives (formal, professional and informal), and is designed to maximise data findability, ensuring compliance and reusability of existing material. In H2IOSC, the model was adopted as already modified by CLARIN⁷, which has invested in promoting standard practices and creating a community of trainers through the CLARIN Trainers' Network⁸. This model enhanced the metadata set by adding specific fields,

⁶⁶ Hoebelheinrich, N. J., et al. Recommendations for a Minimal Metadata Set to Aid Harmonised Discovery of Learning Resources. 1.0, Zenodo, 9 giugno 2022, <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00073>.

⁷ van der Lek, I., et al. Making the CLARIN Training Materials Fair-by-design. Zenodo, 20 gennaio 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699078>.

⁸ <https://www.clarin.eu/trainers-network>

such as **Contributors**, **Workload in ECTS**, **Persistent Identifier** (PID), **Version Date** and **Standard Citation**, making it even more flexible. From the trainers' perspective of applying FAIR principles to learning resources, the most important metadata are those relating to: 1) **keywords**, which can be linked to shared vocabularies specific to the subject area, making the material indexable and easily findable in an institutional repository; 2) the **licences** used, which form the basis for access and reuse possibilities; 3) and finally, fields related to specific educational characteristics such as **target group**, **learning outcome(s)** and **expertise level**, which allow the consistency of the lesson with its educational objectives to be assessed and, if necessary, its reworking to be planned.

Mapping and Harvesting on H2IOSC Marketplace

The **H2IOSC Marketplace** serves as the single access point to all project data, services, and tools, including the two training platforms. Metadata **mapping** plays a crucial role in this integration as both Training Environment and Training Library resources are harvested into the Marketplace using a shared metadata schema aligned with RDA and CLARIN standards.

Controlled vocabularies from **SSHOC Marketplace** and open vocabularies for keywords are applied to improve discoverability. Multilingual metadata and English translations ensure accessibility for international users. This mapping enables interoperability with external platforms and allows researchers, teachers, and students to explore training resources alongside datasets, tools, and services from H2IOSC and related infrastructures. Thus, the Marketplace becomes not only a catalogue but a federated hub where training materials are contextualised with broader scientific resources, significantly enhancing their visibility and reusability.

The **mapping** of metadata was performed on the Marketplace's baseline, matching each metadata label to those of each training platform and their values. For example, the baseline field **Name** of the Marketplace (which indicates the name of the resource in a multilingual format) corresponds to the **Title** field in the RDA metadata set describing the **courses** and the **training materials** in the H2IOSC Training Environment and the Training Library, respectively. These fields contain values, which in most cases are linked either to controlled vocabularies such as TADIRAH⁹ or the SSH Open Marketplace Keyword¹⁰ and ISO standards.

⁹ <https://vocabs.dariah.eu/tadirah/en/>

¹⁰ <https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshomp-keyword/it/?clang=en>

Dissemination and Engagement Activities

Engagement and dissemination events were key to raising awareness among the stakeholders and allowing them to participate in the training events by being informed on the latest developments and the training offer. While a detailed breakdown of these activities can be found in the **H2IOSC WP1 Deliverable 1.3**, below is a report of dissemination and engagement activities directly involved in the general framework of WP8 training activities.

Adaptation and FAIR-ification of existing training modules: WP8 organised dissemination around the translation and adaptation of existing courses (e.g. CLARIN's course originally developed for the UPSKILLS project¹¹ "Introduction to Language Data: Standards and Repositories"). Engagement took place in the form of presentations, workshops, and publications showing how FAIR-by-Design methodology could be applied to training: this dual dissemination–training approach helped reach both students through course environments and teachers/trainers through reusable learning objects.

Joint initiatives with Summer Schools: WP8, particularly via CLARIN-IT, took part in international summer schools such as the *Digital Tools for Humanists* (University of Pisa, 2024, 2025) and the *Lisbon Summer School in Linguistics* (2024). These events were disseminated as training opportunities to the community and later repurposed into modular teaching units (e.g., a course on Linguistic Linked Open Data¹²). Engagement here

¹¹ <https://upskillsproject.eu/>

¹²Khan, A. F., et al. Linguistic Linked Open Data for Humanists. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897931>. Lisbon Summer School in Linguistics, Lisbon, 1-5 July 2024.

was twofold: with students attending the schools, and with the academic networks that collaborated in hosting and publicising them.

Skills4EOSC FAIR-by-Design Training for Trainers: WP8 organised internal dissemination by adapting the FAIR-by-Design Training for Trainers (originally from Skills4EOSC) for the H2IOSC community¹³. This was first directed at consortium members, then re-disseminated to external trainers, ensuring a broader engagement with the methodology. These activities positioned H2IOSC as a bridge between European initiatives and Italian communities, reinforcing external visibility.

National engagement with teachers: via the collaboration with Italian associations, WP8 coordinated with **AIUCD Scuola** and **AICA** to deliver the course “Introduction to Digital Humanities and AI for Schools”. This dissemination/engagement action was targeted at secondary school teachers, a novel public for H2IOSC. The activity combined accredited training (through AICA’s certification role) with open dissemination (through publication of materials in the **H2IOSC Training Environment**). It created a strong link between the academic digital humanities community and the school sector, expanding the project’s engagement reach.¹⁴

Data Stewards and their professionalisation: WP8 engaged with the Italian Community of Data Stewards (in Italian: **Comunità Italiana dei Data Stewards** - CIDS) to align metadata standards and citation practices for training materials. This was both a dissemination action, since WP8 showcased H2IOSC practices during the annual events of the

¹³ For references, see the [Internal Training](#) section of this document.

¹⁴ More on this part in the next section on [Collaborations and Networking](#).

Community¹⁵ and a training-related engagement, ensuring that materials could be reused and cited as proper research output. This strengthened H2IOSC's ties with the broader **Open Science** and **Research Data Management** professional communities.

Dissemination in disciplinary associations: dissemination was carried out in partnership with **AIUCD** in events such as "Aspettando AIUCD" seminars, and annual conferences where WP8 presented its training methodology. Engagement also occurred with **teachers and professionals from cultural heritage institutions** (archives, libraries, museums), ensuring that training materials addressed their needs. These actions showed WP8's ability to transform training outputs into **engagement events that also served dissemination purposes**.

Training materials as dissemination outputs: WP8 emphasised that training materials themselves are research outputs. By publishing courses and learning objects in the H2IOSC platforms, dissemination became continuous: **every deposited object was both a training resource and a dissemination artefact**. Examples of courses disseminated this way:

- van der Lek, I., et al. Introduzione Ai Dati Linguistici: Standard E Archivi Digitali. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13911935>.
- Khan, A. F., et al. Linguistic Linked Open Data for Humanists. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897931>. Lisbon Summer School in Linguistics Lisbon, 1-5 July 2024.
- Introduzione alla Gestione dei Dati Orali, linked to the Italian PRIN project Corpus SIM (in the process of being published).

¹⁵ For references, see the [Collaboration and Networking](#) section.

These were not only training initiatives but also engagement channels with national projects and infrastructures. The result was an ecosystem where training, dissemination, and engagement reinforced each other, expanding H2IOSC's impact well beyond its internal federation.

Collaborations and Networking

The training and engagement activities carried out within the H2IOSC WP8 created a fertile ground for collaboration, networking, and knowledge exchange beyond the operative units formally part of the cluster. By involving external partners at national and international levels, WP8 promoted synergies between research infrastructures, disciplinary associations, professional networks, and educational initiatives.

One of the most significant outcomes of the H2IOSC training program was the establishment of a link with the **Italian Community of Data Stewards**¹⁶, which originated from the **ICDI Competence Centre**¹⁷ in 2023. This professional network gathers specialists responsible for the stewardship, curation, and management of research data across multiple disciplines. Through invited talks and training sessions, H2IOSC experts presented methodologies for **FAIR-by-design educational materials**¹⁸, highlighting how training itself can be designed to meet the FAIR principles. These exchanges reinforced the role of data stewards as multipliers of good practices and opened the door to further collaboration in harmonising training approaches across research infrastructures. The engagement also allowed H2IOSC to be recognised as a stakeholder in the national conversation on data stewardship, ensuring that the heritage science community is represented in cross-disciplinary dialogues about research data management.

¹⁶ https://open-science.it/it/article?rpk=313614&prs_sel=p_datasteward&tpc_sel=t_gestione_dei_dati_della_ricerca. Per il Manifesto della Comunità, si veda: CALDONI, G., et al. Manifesto della comunità italiana data steward (CIDS). Zenodo, 31 marzo 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15129936>.

¹⁷ <https://www.icdi.it/it/attivita/competence-centre>

¹⁸ See materials: <https://zenodo.org/records/14095921> and <https://zenodo.org/records/15582796>

The **CIRCE project**¹⁹ (**Centro Interuniversitario di Ricerca sulla Comunicazione Esemplare**) emerged as another crucial partner. The collaboration involved joint activities such as the public **seminar series on language and accent discrimination**, which were hosted and published on the **H2IOSC Training Environment**. These events, open to the public and strongly interdisciplinary, allowed H2IOSC to reach broader communities concerned with linguistic diversity, inclusivity, and the societal impact of language technologies. Beyond dissemination, these encounters fostered synergies between CIRCE's expertise in linguistic discrimination and H2IOSC's infrastructure approach. Together, they demonstrated how humanities-driven research can engage the public on sensitive topics, while at the same time providing concrete case studies for the development of open and FAIR data resources.

H2IOSC also strengthened ties with academic and professional associations central to the Italian digital humanities and computing communities. **AIUCD - Associazione per l'Informatica Umanistica e la Cultura Digitale** was a key external partner through national conferences and workshops. By participating in AIUCD 2023, 2024 and 2025, H2IOSC placed its training activities within the wider Italian digital humanities ecosystem. This ensured visibility among scholars from various disciplines and encouraged methodological exchanges that may inspire new applications of infrastructures to literary, historical, and linguistic research.

A strong collaboration was also fostered with the **AIUCD interest group on secondary education**²⁰, where H2IOSC WP8 contributed to a course for high school teachers organised by both AIUCD and **AICA - Associazione Italiana per l'Informatica ed il Calcolo Automatico**

¹⁹ <https://www.circe-project.eu/it/home-it/>

²⁰ <https://www.aiucd.it/didattica-scuola/>

to promote the use of digital humanities tools and the safe use of Artificial Intelligence at school.²¹ This course was also hosted on the H2IOSC Training Environment and was officially recognised by the Italian Ministry of Education as a professionalising course for teachers on the S.O.F.I.A. platform. From this teaching experience stemmed further collaboration between H2IOSC WP8, AIUCD school interest group and the **Mamiani high school** in Rome, which is currently developing a pilot curriculum in digital humanities for students²².

The training and engagement records also show contacts with PRIN (Progetti di Ricerca di Rilevante Interesse Nazionale) initiatives and other research infrastructures in Italy, such as the PRIN project **Corpus SIM – Senecta Ipsa Morbus**²³, and the PRIN **Roads to Oral Archives Development and Sustainability (ROADS)**²⁴. These collaborations are particularly valuable because they extend H2IOSC's impact across disciplinary and institutional boundaries. By involving representatives of PRIN projects in training sessions and engagement events, WP8 established bridges with nationally funded research initiatives in linguistics, philology, archaeology, and related fields. These interactions facilitated the cross-fertilisation of methods, datasets, and tools, and they positioned H2IOSC not just as a stand-alone cluster of infrastructures, but as an enabling environment where both H2IOSC and PRIN-funded research can find long-term sustainability and visibility.

Furthermore, specific training events were tailored to the needs of other infrastructures, such as **RESILIENCE ERIC**²⁵, further strengthening the national network. These interactions

²¹ <https://www.aiucd.it/al-via-un-corso-dh-per-i-docenti-delle-scuole-secondarie/>

²² <http://liceomamiani.edu.it/>

²³ <https://www.studiumanistici.unina.it/ricerca/progetti-di-ricerca/progetti-nazionali/progetti-prin/>

²⁴ <https://csc.dei.unipd.it/roads-project/>

²⁵ <https://www.resilience-ri.eu/we-are-resilience/>

demonstrated that H2IOSC is committed to working in a federated way, complementing other initiatives rather than competing with them. This collaborative attitude is crucial for the success of the Italian node in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Other collaborations within the Italian community involved the University of Ferrara, where CLARIN-IT coordinated a pilot to include infrastructural NLP tools into linguistic courses. This collaboration resulted in a teaching pilot spanning from 2023 to 2025, and including two academic years. This resulted in a series of lessons on automatic translation tools, Linked Open Data, and general data management to align the university courses with the best practices shared within the Social Sciences and Humanities community.

At the international level, one of the most significant achievements of H2IOSC training activities was the collaboration with the **CLARIN Trainers' Network**. WP8 actively contributed to CLARIN's training initiatives, also developed in cooperation with other European projects such as Skills4EOSC. By co-designing and delivering training materials together with CLARIN trainers, H2IOSC positioned itself within an international network of experts committed to sharing resources and best practices. This collaboration has multiple benefits as it aligns Italian training initiatives with European standards, ensuring interoperability and reuse, it provides H2IOSC trainers with access to international audiences and feedback, and, finally, it strengthens Italy's role within the ERICs, showcasing national expertise and encouraging further collaborations.

Through the CLARIN Trainers' Network, H2IOSC contributed not only to delivering training but also to shaping training methodologies at the European level. This international networking has long-term value, as it embeds H2IOSC in the global conversation about

open and FAIR training design. One of the most valuable outputs of this collaboration were the workshops organised in international conferences, such as the one called "*Applying FAIR data principles in corpus linguistics*", co-located with the Conference Corpus Linguistics 2025, and the CLARIN Cafè on Translation Technologies, held in June 2024 and originated from the teaching experience at the University of Ferrara: vd. Frontini, F., et al. CLARIN Café Teaching & Training Translation Technologies in SSH Disciplines. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12703633>.

Further participation in national and international conferences has also made it possible to expand networking and opportunities for contact with different types of stakeholders. Participation in the Digital Heritage 2025 conference (8–12 September, Siena, Italy) with the oral presentation "Bridging Disciplines for Heritage Professionals: The H2IOSC Digital Training Platform (by CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS and OPERAS)" as well as the presentation "Building a FAIR Training Ecosystem for the Social Science and Humanities within the H2IOSC project"²⁶ at the DARIAH Annual Event 2025 – The Past provided an important opportunity to showcase H2IOSC WP8 activities to a wide international audience. This last session helped raise awareness of the digital training platform and library, highlighted their value for the cultural heritage community, and stimulated constructive discussion on the sustainability and future development of H2IOSC training initiatives.

Through these collaborations, H2IOSC has positioned itself as both a national hub and an international partner, capable of building bridges across disciplines, sectors, and countries. The networking established through training and engagement is thus one of the most

²⁶ Spadi, Alessia, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Francesca Frontini, Giulia Pedonese, Lucia Francalanci, Alessia Scognamiglio, Pietro Restaneo, et al. Building a FAIR Training Ecosystem for the Social Science and Humanities Within the H2IOSC Project. Zenodo, 27 giugno 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15755151>

enduring legacies of the project, paving the way for future collaborations in open science and cultural heritage research.

CONCLUSIONS

The activities carried out within WP8 of the H2IOSC project have significantly advanced training, capacity building, and engagement in the field of digital humanities and cultural heritage. The project succeeded in creating a rich ecosystem of training opportunities directed at both internal personnel and external user communities, while also laying the foundations for long-term sustainability through the development of two dedicated platforms: the **H2IOSC Training Environment** and the **H2IOSC Training Library**.

Internally, the project strengthened the skills of H2IOSC personnel through targeted upskilling activities, including workshops, webinars, and the H2IOSC Cafés series, which promoted cross-infrastructure knowledge exchange. Externally, WP8 reached a broad and diverse audience, spanning students, researchers, educators, professionals, and even the general public. By tailoring training to multiple audiences and disciplinary needs, the project ensured that digital tools and open science practices became accessible and relevant across communities.

The adoption of the **FAIR-by-Design methodology**, developed in synergy with the Skills4EOSC initiative, represents a major achievement. This methodology not only guaranteed the quality, findability, and reusability of training materials but also aligned H2IOSC with European best practices. Its implementation in courses and modular training objects further enhanced the project's interoperability with broader open science infrastructures.

Dissemination and engagement activities, including collaborations with summer schools, disciplinary associations, and professional networks such as the Italian Community of Data Stewards, expanded the visibility and impact of H2IOSC. At the international level,

contributions to the CLARIN Trainers' Network embedded the project into a European training ecosystem, ensuring its outputs resonate beyond national boundaries. Collaborations with national and international initiatives further demonstrated the project's ability to create meaningful synergies and position itself as a federated partner in the European Open Science Cloud landscape.

Despite these achievements, some actions to be implemented remain. These key technical and infrastructural features to implement include:

- distribution of **DOIs for training materials** in the H2IOSC Training Library;
- mechanism for issuing **certifications via the European Digital Credentials** framework;
- final deployment of the **Training Environment** and the **Training Library** on the **H2IOSC Data Centre**, as well as their full integration with the **H2IOSC Marketplace**.

However, the remaining infrastructural gaps will be addressed in the following months to ensure that the platforms and resources developed can function as a fully operational, integrated part of the H2IOSC ecosystem.

In conclusion, WP8 has made substantial progress in building both human and digital capacities for open science in the humanities and cultural heritage sectors. Its achievements in training, methodology development, and international networking represent solid and lasting contributions for the long-term success and visibility of the federation.

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To view the full list of publications and events, please refer to Annex 2 – *Publications* and Annex 1 – *Dissemination and Engagement* of Deliverable 1.3 (M36).

To access the published courses, register for free on the [H2IOSC Training Environment](#) platform, or browse the [course catalogue](#) available on the project portal.

To consult the reusable teaching materials, freely access the [H2IOSC Training Library](#) platform.